

PE12

Study of Mechanical and Structural properties of PCL/TCP composite using Selective Laser Sintering

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Abstract

The objective of this study is to find advancement in applications of additive manufacturing in tissue engineering scaffolds. There's a self-importance of Selective Laser Sintering and therefore understanding its methodology and study of its applications is needed. In this work the objective of the study was exploring applications and development of SLS in Tissue Engineering. We identified other AM technologies associated with tissue engineering, depending upon the material selected. We found a polymer composite, called polycaprolactone - tricalcium phosphate (PCL/TCP) which is suitable to be processed with SLS technique. We found in our study how mechanical and structural properties of PCL/TCP composite are influenced by the concentration of constituents in the composite. We found supporting research studies where study of the concentration of constituents was carried to find its resulting influence on mechanical and structural properties. We concluded how an appropriate concentration of constituents can provide best desired properties. The limitations, challenges and scope for future work are also addressed in the study.

1. Introduction

In today's technological advancement, there's increasing requirement of making components which are dimensionally precise, are light in weight compared to ordinary metals, and possess properties similar to them. With the advent of additive manufacturing, it has become easy to manufacture components which were assumed to be very difficult to produce or manufacture some years ago. Additive Manufacturing (AM) presents freedom for design as well as ability to manufacture single or multiple components from a wide range of materials. The Additive manufacturing method has the potential to produce fully dense parts/components in a short time, with higher precision. The purpose of this study is to explore the development and applications of polymer composite (Polycaprolactone - tricalcium phosphate) using Selective Laser Sintering for tissue engineering (TE) scaffold. The study is useful to provide future directions of AM used for TE scaffold. Every AM technique is a process based on the unique property of the raw materials applied suited to achieve desired property and application. The study also addresses challenges associated with fabrication of TE scaffolds, such as expanding the range of materials, improving precision and adapting to complex scaffold structures. Current techniques of Scaffold-based AM and scaffold-free AM (bio/organ printing) are promising and will still go in parallel during a period of time in future.

1.1 Selective laser sintering (SLS)

SLS was developed by Carl Deckard for his master's thesis at the University of Texas and patented in 1989 [3]. A CO₂ laser is used to melt polymeric powder and form part geometries without using any toxic chemicals, blowing agents or support structures. SLS materials are suited for direct functional applications where robust performance characteristics are required [1]. 3D objects are fabricated by selectively sintering the cross-sectional area of

each layer of powder material in a powder bed using a CO₂ laser [3]. Heating of material till its glass transition temperature is done prior to fusing by the laser. Each layer of scanned powder is fused to its underlying layer and corresponds to a cross section of the object as determined from a mathematical slicing operation. The schematic diagram of SLS system is as shown in the Figure 1.

Figure 1 Schematic of the laser sintering process [2]

A wide variety of materials are processed using Selective Laser Sintering. They can be categorised as:

Polymer material: nylon/polymide (PA) ,Polysterene , Elastomers, and Composites.

Metals and Alloys: 316L steel, Laserform A6, LaserForm™ ST-100 Powder, LaserForm ST-200, 17-4 Stainless Steel, 15-5 Stainless Steel, Cobalt Chrome, Maraging Steel MS1, M2 high-speed steel, Inco 718 and 625, Aluminium Alloy AlSi10MG, Titanium Ti6Al4V / ELI.

2. SLS in Tissue Engineering

Tissue engineering is an interdisciplinary field which integrates principles of the life sciences with engineering to develop alternatives for the replacement and repair of human tissue and organs. In recent years, SLS technique has been explored to fabricate tissue engineering scaffolds and porous implants consisted mainly of polymer/ceramic and composites biocompatible polymers [2]. A major research area of this field is the utilization of three-dimensional scaffold structures composed of natural or synthetic polymers that enable the restoration, maintenance, or enhancement of living tissues and organs [4]. They are typically endowed with complex internal architecture, channels, and porosity for providing sites for cell attachment and proliferation, and conveying cells, growth factors, and bio-molecular signals to promote tissue regeneration at the implantation site. Earlier scaffold fabrication relied on a variety of techniques ,like using woven and non-woven fibre-based fabrics, particulate leaching and solvent casting , phase separation, melt-molding, injection molding, forging, high pressure processing, and cold or hot pressing .However, these methods do not provide adequate control over porosity, porous architecture of the scaffold and its exterior geometry. Thus, there's need of versatile fabrication methods which can address these factors. Selective laser sintering (SLS) has various advantages in the construction of biodegradable synthetic polymer scaffolds that have complex geometries[4]

3. Polycaprolactone – tricalcium phosphate (PCL/TCP) composite for TE scaffold

Biodegradable synthetic polymers which have applications in tissue engineering scaffolds are polyglycolic acid (PGA), poly (lactic-co-glycolic acid) (PLGA), polycaprolactone (PCL),

along metals, say titanium. The key advantages include the ability to tailor mechanical properties and degradation kinetics to suit various applications [9]. Polycaprolactone is among the most suitable candidates, the reason being its availability, variable biodegradability, and good mechanical properties. Also, research reveals a bioactive nature of polycaprolactone - tricalcium phosphate (PCL/TCP) scaffolds by nucleating the formation of hydroxyapatite on its surface when soaked in simulated body fluids. Poly (ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL) is a semicrystalline, bioresorbable polymer belonging to the aliphatic polyester family, with a melting point of 60 °C and a high decomposition temperature of 350 °C and β -Tricalcium phosphate (β -TCP) is a bioactive and biocompatible ceramic which has a stoichiometry similar to that of the amorphous inorganic phase of bones [8].

3.1 Mechanical and Structural properties of PCL/TCP Composite

Significant studying and developing new polymer composites have lead to advancement in Tissue Engineering and its integration with additive manufacturing technology. A study was conducted to determine and prepare finite element model of tensile and compressive mechanical properties for both solid polycaprolactone (PCL) and porous PCL scaffolds with one-dimensional, two-dimensional and three-dimensional orthogonal, periodic porous architectures produced by selective laser sintering (SLS) [5]. Optimum processing parameters were used to ensure scaffolds with nearly full density (>95%) in the designed part and excellent geometric and dimensional control (within 3–8% of design), the material being processed using a Sinterstation® 2000 commercial SLS machine (3D Systems Inc., Valencia, CA).

Table 1 Optimal SLS parameter settings for processing PCL [7]

Parameter	Setting	
	Solid	Scaffold
Laser power	4.1 W	4.1 W
Scan speed	1079.5 mm s ⁻¹	1079.5 mm s ⁻¹
Scan spacing	152.4 μ m	152.4 μ m
Part bed temperature	46 °C	46 °C
Powder layer delay	0 s	8 s

Table 2 Mechanical property assessment of bulk and porous SLS processed PCL [5]

Property	Unit	SLS					
		Solid gage section		Porous gage section ¹			
		//	\perp	1D	2D	3D	
Tension	Elastic modulus, E	MPa	363.4 \pm 71.6	343.9 \pm 33.2	140.5 \pm 19.6	42.0 \pm 6.9	35.5 \pm 5.8
	0.2% Offset yield strength, σ_Y	MPa	8.2 \pm 1.0	10.1 \pm 1.5	3.2 \pm 0.6	0.67 \pm 0.08	0.67 \pm 0.06
	Strain at yield, ϵ_Y	-	0.024 \pm 0.006	0.031 \pm 0.002	0.024 \pm 0.001	0.017 \pm 0.002	0.020 \pm 0.002
	Ultimate tensile strength, σ_{UT}	MPa	10.5 \pm 0.3	16.1 \pm 0.3	4.5 \pm 0.4	1.2 \pm 0.2	1.1 \pm 0.1
	Strain at break, ϵ_B	-	0.043 \pm 0.007	8.0 \pm 0.3	0.095 \pm 0.022	0.092 \pm 0.022	0.096 \pm 0.025
Compression	Elastic modulus, E	MPa	297.8 \pm 7.1	317.1 \pm 3.9	133.4 \pm 2.6	12.1 \pm 0.5	14.9 \pm 0.6
	0.2% Offset yield strength, σ_Y	MPa	12.5 \pm 0.3	10.3 \pm 0.2	4.25 \pm 0.05	0.45 \pm 0.01	0.42 \pm 0.03
	Strain at yield, ϵ_Y	-	0.052 \pm 0.003	0.037 \pm 0.002	0.0370 \pm 0.000	0.0376 \pm 0.001	0.0268 \pm 0.003
	Ultimate compressive strength	MPa	38.7 \pm 0.3	38.80 \pm 0.66	10.0 \pm 0.62	0.60 \pm 0.00	0.60 \pm 0.00

Note: $\mu \pm \sigma$ where μ denotes the mean and σ denotes the standard deviation ($n = 6$).

¹ Porous compressive specimens tested parallel to SLS build direction, porous tensile specimens tested perpendicular to SLS build direction.

² Reported by Perstorp Caprolactone, tests were conducted at a strain rate of 10 mm min⁻¹ to determine E and 100 mm min⁻¹ in all other cases.

Figure 2 Sub-domain plots of von Mises stress distribution for (a) porous tensile test specimen (b) porous compressive test specimen [5]

Results from this study establish the basis for successfully achieving, via SLS, physical realizations of PCL scaffolds with targeted mechanical properties predicted through a priori FEA of the corresponding three-dimensional scaffold designs.

In another study, optimal fabrications of tissue engineering scaffolds made of polycaprolactone (PCL) composites filled with different volume fractions (10-30%) of tricalcium phosphate (TCP) was performed using selective laser sintering (SLS) process[4]. Design of Experiment (DOE) was used to find optimal SLS processing parameters for each composition of materials, followed by evaluation of compressive mechanical properties of solid PCL/TCP composites and structures with various types of periodic porous architectures produced by SLS. A gradual degradation of the compressive mechanical properties of test specimens from 0-DIR to 3-DIR are found due to the increasing porosity, though no clear degradation of mechanical property from 2-DIR to 3-DIR could be found.

Figure 3 Compressive modulus of PCL/TCP composite as a function of (a) TCP volume fraction, (b) Directional Porosity [4]

The study concludes that 3-DIR porous structure with more than 20% TCP composites is highly preferable [4].

In one of the recent studies, influence of wt% of β -TCP and PCL particle sizes on material microstructure and mechanical properties was studied, with increasing ceramic content causing a small but significant increase in stiffness but significant reductions in strength [5]. SLS scaffold materials were fabricated from PCL and from PCL with two volume fractions of β -TCP. First assessment was of the effect of increasing ceramic content on material microstructure and elastic properties. Second evaluation was of degradation of these

materials which was achieved using accelerated ageing to replicate in-vivo degradation at 14 weeks.

Figure 4 Summary of the degradation study of mechanical testing data for PCL (grey), 90/10 wt%(blue) and 50/50 wt % struts (red) .The change in elastic modulus for each material is shown in (A), the change in tensile strength is shown in (B) and the change in strain at the tensile strength is shown in (C) [6].

Figure 5 CT scan images of PCL, 90/10 wt% and 50/50 wt% PCL/ β -TCP struts (left to right) with zero degradation (top) and after 7 weeks degradation (bottom). White arrows point to β -TCP particles [6]

Study shows slight reduction in mechanical properties while incorporating 50 wt% volume of β -TCP particles in this type of scaffold material, and a slight increase in degradation, compared to the 90/10 wt% material. The results here suggest that the small reduction in mechanical properties with increased ceramic content is more than compensated for by the expected increase in bone formation [6].

Conclusion

SLS technique is one of the most important and useful process for various applications. This technique is time – efficient and provides one of the best design freedoms. In our research study, we have observed the impact of varying concentrations in composition of PCL/TCP scaffolds.

- A computational model for studying tensile and compressive mechanical properties of bulk PCL processed to near-full density through SLS serving as baseline mechanical properties for FEA has been successfully designed with the agreement between experimentally measured and computationally modelled mechanical properties of scaffold designs and demonstrated the capability of designing scaffolds endowed with 1D, 2D and 3D orthogonally porous scaffolds for bone tissue engineering with desirable mechanical properties.
- This study provides invaluable information for further developing and fabricating TE scaffolds with adequate mechanical properties and desirable porosity for applications. The reduction in stiffness due to degradation was greater for composite struts than for PCL struts, making β -TCP constituent material more ductile due to degradation. Such results illustrate the complexity of polymer–ceramic SLS material microstructures, and the influence of material composition on their properties. The resulting mechanical properties, and changes during degradation, should be considered for the design of orthopaedic scaffolds for critical-sized defects.
- Scaffold-based AM and scaffold-free AM (bio/organ printing) are the techniques which will continue to evolve in future. The only disadvantage associated is that cells have to be implanted or “seeded” into scaffold to culture tissue, and cells only attach on the surfaces of the strands in scaffold, whereas for bio/organ printing, success in fabrication of functional organs highly depends on advancement in cell attachment and growing technology.

References

- [1] K.R. Bakshi, A. V. Mulay, “A Review on Selective Laser Sintering: A Rapid Prototyping Technology”, IOSR Journal of Mechanical & Civil Engineering, e-ISSN: 2278-1684, pp 53-57
- [2] Rajesh R, Sudheer S, M V Kulkarni, “Selective Laser Sintering Process –A Review”, ISSN (PRINT): 2393-8374, Vol. 2, No. 10
- [3] Yan Li, D Li, B lu, D Gao, F Zhou, “ Current status of additive manufacturing for tissue engineering scaffold”, Rapid Prototyping Journal, Vol. 21, Iss 6, 2015, pp. 747 – 762
- [4] H Chung, H Jee, S Das, “Selective laser sintering of PCL/TCP composites for tissue engineering scaffolds”, Journal of Mechanical Science and Technology 24 (2010) 241~244
- [5] S Eshraghi, Suman Das, “Mechanical and microstructural properties of polycaprolactone scaffolds with one-dimensional, two-dimensional, and three-dimensional orthogonally oriented porous architectures produced by selective laser sintering”, Acta Biomaterialia 6 (2010) 2467–2476
- [6] H Doyle, S Lohfeld, P McHugh, “Evaluating the effect of increasing ceramic content on the mechanical properties, material microstructure and degradation of selective laser sintered polycaprolactone/ β -tricalcium phosphate materials”, Medical Engineering and Physics 37 (2015) 767–776
- [7] Partee B, Hollister SJ, Das S. , “Selective laser sintering process optimization for layered manufacturing of CAPA_ 6501 polycaprolactone bone tissue engineering scaffolds” , J Manuf Science Eng Trans ASME 2006;128(2):531–40.
- [8] C Lam, S H Teoh, D W Hutmacher, “Comparison of the degradation of polycaprolactone and polycaprolactone– (β -tricalcium phosphate) scaffolds in alkaline medium”, Polym Int 56:718–728 (2007).
- [9] P.A Gunatillake, R Adhikari, “ Biodegradable Synthetic Polymers For Tissue Engineering”, European Cells and Materials, Vol. 5. 2003
- [10] Y B Kim, G Kim, “ Functionally graded PCL/ β -TCP biocomposites in a multilayered structure for bone tissue regeneration”, Appl Phys A (2012) 108:949–959